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Review Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Energy Drink

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ABSTRACT

Ayurvedic formulations are mainly administered by oral route, and most of the orally administered. Ayurvedic formulations belong to liquid form of drug. Polyherbal energy drink was prepared by using some traditional herbs having proved nutritional potential. The ingredients were selected as Amla, Liquorice, Ashwagandha, Tulsi, and Mentha. The prepared polyherbal energy drink was evaluated immediately after preparation. The analysis of prepared drink found to contain optimum level of pH. The developed herbal energy drink provides good taste combined with potential health benefits. The prepared drink is potentially capable to replace the synthetic drinks available in the market. These drinks are marketed for young people actively involved in sports or overworking hours, as natural alternatives that increase fun and improve physical and cognitive performances such as attention, concentration and alertness. There are commonly held false perceptions that the consumption of EDs can rectify the impairment to human physiology because of alcohol consumption including visual reaction time and motor coordination, which is highly required for sports and driving activities, to name a few.

INTRODUCTION

India has used the herbal drugs long safe and continuous uses in alternative Medicines well as over the counter self-medications by Ayurveda doctors. Its definition was "any substance that may be considered food or part of food and provides medical or health benefits, including the prevention and treatment of disease. The consumption of energy drinks has increased

vigorously among the youth generation, even after knowing the fact that the energy drinks have adverse effects. The energy drinks available in the market contains varying amount of caffeine but it has its own side effects. The preparation contains poly herbs such as Amla, Liquorice, Ashwagandha, Tulsi, and Mentha leaves have proved pharmacological activity with no side effects.

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Amla: Amla, also known as Indian gooseberry, is rich in vitamin C and antioxidants. It is believed to boost immunity and promote overall health.

Ashwagandha: Ashwagandha is an adaptogenic herb that has been used in Ayurvedic medicine for centuries. It is known for its potential to reduce stress, improve cognitive function, and boost energy levels.

Liquorice: Liquorice root is often used as a natural sweetener and flavoring agent. It can add a carminative effect to energy drink.

Tulsi: Tulsi, also known as holy basil, is considered a sacred herb in Ayurveda. It is believed to have various health benefits, including boosting immunity, reducing stress, and promoting respiratory health.

Mentha: Mentha, or mint, is known for its refreshing and cooling properties. It can provide a pleasant flavor and aroma to your energy drink.

Honey: Honey is a natural sweetener that can provide a quick source of energy. It also contains antioxidants and has potential antibacterial properties.

Methyl paraben: Methyl paraben is a preservative commonly used in food and cosmetic products to prevent the growth of bacteria and fungi.

The polyherbal energy drink is the best choice for the replacement of soft energy drinks usage and tackles the adverse effects. Herbal ingredients play an important role in the sensory evaluation of energy drinks as well as improving their health has beneficial effects. Herbal extracts are the commonly consumed drinks/beverages, which are brewed from several parts of plants.

Review Of Literature

Komal R. More and Shraddha et al(2024)M. Jain Most of herbal syrup was originally derived from plant herbal medicine refers to use extract of fruit for medicinal purpose. Alongwith other dosage from herbal drugs also formulated inform of syrups. Today syrup is used for treatment of many ailments and to overcome symptoms of diseases Ms. Jaini K. Patel, Dr. Divyakant Patel, Mr. Ronak Patel, Mr. Janak A. Akbari, Mr. Abhishek Mishra et al(2023) In the present study, poly-herbal powder drink was developed using traditional herbs that proved nutritional potential. The key ingredients were selected as cinnamon, Amla, liquorice, lemon juice, tulsi, and mentha based on their household routine use in the summer with proven refreshing, cooling, and energetic feeling for ages. After several trials made, the final composition of the formulation was selected as the most suitable combination based on the taste and physicochemical properties. The physicochemical analysis of the prepared drink was found to contain an optimum level of Ph which was following the commercial recommendations. Ms. Chetana D. Patil, Ms. Mayuri B. Bhandhari, Ms. Smita P. Bedis, et al (2022) Ayurvedic formulations belong to liquid form of drug. Polyherbal energy drink was prepared by using some traditional herbs having proved nutritional potential. The ingredients were selected as Amla, Liquorice, Ashwagandha, Tulsi, and Mentha. The prepared polyherbal energy drink was evaluated immediately after preparation. The analysis of prepared drink found to contain optimum level of pH. The developed herbal energy drink provides good taste combined with potential health benefits Vikas Gawali. 5.Shreya Talreja, Sonam Kumari, Prateek Srivastava, and Swarnima Pandey et al(2019) Phyllanthus emblica Linn. Or Emblica officinalis Gaertn. commonly known as Indian gooseberry or Amla. Emblica officinalis (Amla) are widely used in the Indian system of medicine (Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha). According to

believe in ancient Indian mythology, it is the first tree to be created in the universe. It belongs to the family of Euphorbiaceae. It is the richest natural source of Vitamin C. *Emblica officinalis* (EO) primarily contains tannins, phenolic compounds, amino acids and carbohydrates. Its fruit juice contains the highest amount of vitamin C, Ellagic acid, Chebulinic acid, Quercetin, Chebulagic acid, Emblicanin-A, Emblicanin-B, Gallic acid and ascorbic acid etc. Dalvi Nilam, Mahesh Bhal Singh. et al(2018) In the present study, poly-herbal powder drink was developed by using some traditional herbs having proved nutritional potential. The key ingredients were selected as cinnamon, Amla, liquorice, lemon juice, tulsi and menthe based on their household routine use in the summer with proven refreshing, cooling and energetic feeling since ages. After several trials made, the final composition of formulation was selected as most suitable combination based on the taste and physicochemical properties. The physicochemical analysis of the prepared drink found to contain optimum level of pH which was in accordance of the commercial recommendations. During the nine point's hedonic scalesensory evaluation, the drink was strongly liked for colour, taste, flavor and texture. The developed herbal drink provides an economical and feasible option for the consumers with very good taste combined with potential health benefits. The present drink is potentially capable to replace the synthetic drinks available in the market Anhinav Pandey, Rishabh Dixit ,Alok Prakash ,and V.Devi Rajeswari et al(2014) Energydrinks (EDs) are caffeine-based beverages that commonly contains large amount of carbohydrates, sugar, health supplements and various energy stimulants, such as ginseng and vitamin B, to name a few. These drinks are marketed for young people actively involved in sports or overworking hours, as natural alternatives that increases fun and improve

physical and cognitive performances such as attention, concentration and alertness. Natalie Ohanessian et al(2009) The objective of this project is to develop a natural tea based energy drink with minimal and all natural sugars. When a consumer walks into a conventional grocery store, different energy drink choices are available. The one thing almost all these energy beverages have in common is the extremely high level of caffeine. There is a demand for consumers looking for a "natural" energy boost

3. Rationale Of the Study: -

Need Of Work: -

The need for a polyherbal energy drink arises from several factors that align with current consumer demands and market trends. Many consumers are looking for natural alternatives to synthetic energy drinks that often contain high levels of caffeine, sugar, or artificial ingredients. Polyherbal energy drinks use a blend of herbs known for their natural energy-boosting properties, offering a healthier option. With increasing awareness of health and wellness, people are seeking drinks that not only provide energy but also contribute to overall well-being. A polyherbal drink can offer additional benefits such as improved focus, stress reduction, and immune support, thanks to the medicinal properties of the herbs used. There is a growing demand for functional beverages drinks that do more than just quench thirst. A polyherbal energy drink meets this demand by offering functional benefits, like enhanced vitality, stamina

Objectives: -

1. To study the Amla, Ashwagandha, Liquorice, Tulsi and their beneficial properties
2. To study the Polyherbal Energy Drink their different preparation.
3. To study their medicinal uses.

4. Support Immune System

Plan Of Work: -

1. Selection of pure drug

- Amla
- Ashwagandha
- Liquorice
- Tulsi
- Honey
- Mentha

2. Collection of Crude Drug

3. Preparation of material and methods

4. Selection of the effective method of preparation.

5. Experimental design-

Formulation and preparation of Polyherbal Energy Drink

6. Result & discussion

7. Conclusion

8. Reference

5. Drug Profile

1. Amla

Fig no 4.1: Amla Synonyms: Emblica, Indian goose berry, amla

Biological Source

This consists of dried, as well as fresh fruits of the plant *Emblica officinalis* Gaerth (*Phyllanthusemblica* Linn.), belonging to family Euphorbiaceae.

Chemical Constituent

It is highly nutritious and is an important dietary source of vitamin C, minerals, and amino acids. The edible fruit tissue contains protein concentration 3-fold and ascorbic acid concentration 160- fold compared to that of the apple. The fruit also contains considerably higher concentration of most minerals and amino acids than apples. The pulpy portion of fruit, dried and freed from the nuts contains: gallic acid 1.32%, tannin, sugar 36.10%; gum 13.75%; albumin 13.08%; crude cellulose 17.08%; mineral matter 4.12%; and moisture 3.83%. Tannins are the mixture of gallic acid, ellagic acid, and phyllembin

Uses

The fruits are diuretic, acrid, cooling, refrigerant, and laxative. Dried fruit is useful in haemorrhage, diarrhoea, diabetes, and dysentery. They are useful in the disorders associated with the digestive system and are also prescribed in the treatment of jaundice and coughs. It has antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral activities. Amla is one of the three ingredients of the famous ayurvedic preparation, triphala, which is given to treat chronic dysentery, biliousness, and other disorders, and it is also an ingredient in chavanpras

Ashwagandha

Fig no 4.2 : Ashwagandha

Synonyms: Ashwagandha, Clustered Wintercherry.

Biological Source

It consists of the dried roots and stem bases of *Withania somnifera* Dunal, belonging to family Solanaceae.

Chemical Constituents

The plants contain the alkaloid withanine as the main constituent and somniferine, pseudowithanine, tropine and pseudotropine, hygrine, isopellelerine, anaferine,

anahygrine and steroid lactones. The leaves contain steroid lactone, commonly known as withanolides

Uses

All plant parts are used including the roots, bark, leaves, fruit and seed are used to treat nervous disorders, intestinal infections and leprosy. Ashwagandha is one of the most widespread tranquillizers used in India, where it holds a position of importance similar to ginseng in China. It acts mainly on the reproductive and nervous systems, having a rejuvenative effect on the body, and is used to improve vitality and aid recovery after chronic illness. It is also used to treat nervous exhaustion, debility, insomnia, wasting diseases, failure to thrive in children, impotence, infertility; multiple sclerosis, etc. Externally it has been applied as a poultice to boils, swellings and other painful parts. Withania is considered as an adaptogen and so is used in number of diseases Balya, vajikari, vajigandha, varahakarni, turangagandha, hayagandha, kushthagandhi

Liquorice

Fig no 4.3: Liquorice Synonyms: Radix Glycyrrhizae, Sweet liquorice.

Biological Source

Liquorice consists of subterranean peeled and unpeeled stolons, roots and subterranean stems of

Glycyrrhiza glabra Linn, and other species of *Glycyrrhiza*, belonging to family Leguminosae.

Chemical Constituents

The chief constituent of liquorice root is Glycyrrhizin (6–8%), obtainable in the form of a sweet, which is 50 times sweeter than sucrose, white crystalline powder, consisting of the calcium and potassium salts of glycyrrhizic acid. Glycyrrhizic acid on hydrolysis yields glycyrrhetic or Glycyrrhetic Acid.

Uses Glycyrrhiza is widely used as a sweetening agent and in bronchial problems such as catarrh, bronchitis, cold, flu and coughs. It reduces irritation of the throat and yet has an expectorant

action. It produces its demulcent and expectorant effects. It is used in relieving stress. It is a potent healing agent for tuberculosis, where its effects have been compared to hydrocortisone. Glycyrrhiza is also effective in helping to reduce fevers (glycyrrhetic acid has an effect like aspirin), and it may have an antibacterial action as well. It is used in the treatment of chronic inflammations such as arthritis.

Tulsi

Fig 4.4 : Tulsi

Synonyms

Sacred basil, basil.

Biological Source

Tulsi consists of fresh and dried leaves of *Ocimum sanctum* Linn., belonging to family Labiatae.

Chemical Constituents

Tulsi leaves contain bright, yellow coloured and pleasant volatile oil (0.1 to 0.9%). The oil content of the drug varies depending upon the type, the place of cultivation and season of its collection. The oil is collected by steam distillation method from the leaves and flowering tops. It contains approximately 70% eugenol, carvacrol (3%), and eugenol-methyl-ether (20%). It also contains

caryophyllin. Seeds contain fixed oil with good drying properties.

Uses

The fresh leaves, its juice and volatile oil are used for various purposes. The oil is antibacterial and insecticidal. The leaves are used as stimulant, aromatic, spasmolytic, and diaphoretic. The juice is used as an antiperiodic and as a constituent of several preparations for skin diseases and also to cure earache. Infusion of the leaves is used as a stomachic. The drug is a good immunomodulatory agent.

Honey

Fig no 4.5 : Honey Synonyms: Madhu, Madh, Mel, Purified Honey.

Biological Source

Honey is a viscid and sweet secretion stored in the honey comb by various species of bees, such as *Apis mellifera*, *Apis dorsata*, *Apis florea*, *Apis indica* and other species of *Apis*, belonging to family Apidae (Order: Hymenoptera).

Chemical Constituents

The average composition of honey is as follows: Moisture 14–24%, Dextrose 23–36%, Levulose (Fructose) 30–47%, Sucrose 0.4–6%, Dextrin and Gums 0–7% and Ash 0.1–0.8%. Besides, it is found to contain small amounts of essential oil, beeswax, pollen grains, formic acid, acetic acid, succinic acid, maltose, dextrin, colouring pigments, vitamins and an admixture of enzymes, for example, diastase, invertase and inulase.

Uses

Honey shows mild laxative, bactericidal, sedative, antiseptic and alkaline characters. It is used for cold, cough, fever, sore eye and throat, tongue and duodenal ulcers, liver disorders, constipation, diarrhoea, kidney and other urinary disorders, pulmonary tuberculosis, marasmus, rickets, scurvy and insomnia. It is applied as a remedy on open wounds after surgery.

Mentha

Fig no 4.6: Mentha

Synonyms: Spearmint, Garden mint, Mackerel mint, Our lady's mint, Green mint, Sage of Bethlehem.

Biological Source

Pudina consists of dried leaves and flowering tops of *Mentha spicata* Linn., belonging to family Labiatae.

Chemical Constituents

It contains about 0.5% volatile oil containing carvone. It also contains limonene, phellandrine, dihydrocarveol acetate, esters of acetic, butyric, and caproic or caprylic acids. The drug also contains resin and tannins.

Uses

The drug is used as spice, flavouring agent, carminative, digestive, spasmolytic, stimulant, and as a diuretic. Pudina is chiefly used for culinary purposes. Sweetened infusion is an excellent remedy for infantile trouble and also a pleasant beverage in fevers, inflammatory diseases.

Methods And Preparation

Fig no: 5.1

Collection of drug

The powder of Amla, Ashwagandha, Liquorice, Tulsi, Mentha was collected from shabbarDawasaz clinic.

The Authentication of drug done by following methods:

Physical Analysis:

1. Amla

- Colour: Light Greenish yellow
- Odour: Pungent
- Taste: Sour

2. Ashwagandha

- Colour: brownish white
- Odour: Slightly bitter and earthy
- Taste: Pungent, sweet

3. Liquorice:

- Colour: Black
- Odour: Aniseed and caramel
- Taste: Sweet

4. Tulsi

- Colour : Green or purple
- Odour: Fragrant aroma
- Taste : Astringen

5. Mentha

- Colour : Green
- Odour : Pungent
- Taste : Sweet taste

6. Honey

- Water test

Mix a tablespoon of honey into a glass of water. Pure honey will settle at the bottom and not dissolve easily. Impure honey may dissolve or create a cloudy appearance.

- Heat test

Gently heat a small amount of honey. Pure honey will caramelize and take on a golden hue. Impure honey may burn or smell burnt.

Formulation Table

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Qty Given	Uses
1	Amla	13.9gm	Immunity Booster
2	Liquorice	13.9gm	Carminative Expectorant
3	Ashwagandha	13.9gm	Anti-Oxidant
4	Tulsi	4.8gm	Antibacterial
5	Mentha	3.5gm	Flavouring Agent
6	Honey	Qty. Sufficient	Sweetening Agent
7	Methyl Paraben	0.4gm	Preservative
8	Water	400ml	Vehicle

Procedure:

All the ingredients were weighed accurately and then mixed with 400ml of water, the mixture was boiled until total volume becomes one fourth of initial volume. Then the decoction was cooled and

filtered. After cooling addition of sufficient amount of honey is mixed with drink and then required quantity of methyl paraben will be added as preservative to the mixture. Prepared drink will be filled into a tight container. The final herbal drink was then subjected for evaluation.

Fig 5.2: Preparation of Poly Herbal Energy Drink

Evaluation of Polyherbal Energy Drink:

1. Physical appearance

The polyherbal energy drink was examined for physical appearance in terms of colour, Odour, Taste.

2. Test for carbohydrates

1-2 drops of dilute iodine + 1-2 ml of sample which shows red or brown colour.

3. Test for alkaloids Dragondroff's test:

2-3 ml sample + few drops of Dragondroff's reagent solution turns into orange brown ppt.

4. Test for flavonoids

Small amount of sample mixed with lead acetate solution which shows yellow ppt.

5. Test for tannins and phenolic compounds

Small amount of sample + acetic acid which gives red colour.

6. Test for proteins

2ml of sample + 2 ml of biuret reagent then mix vigorously solution shows purple colour

7. Test for fats :

Take small amount of sample on piece of filter paper, dry the paper in sunlight, observe the paper, oily patch on the paper indicates that presence of fat.

8. Determination of pH

The pH of energy drink was checked by using a calibrated digital pH meter at constant temperature and the pH was noted.

Table 2: Physical Evaluation

Colour	Reddish brown
Odour	Pleasant
Taste	Sweet
pH	4.35

1. Phytochemical Tests for Ingredients:

Table 3: Phytochemical Tests for Ingredients

Phytochemical Test	Observation
For Amla: alcoholic or aqueous extract of the drug+ferric chloride solution	Blue colour observed
For Ashwagandha: Wagner's test: Wagner's reagent + aqueous solution of ashwagandha	Brown precipitate
For Liquorice: 80% sulphuric acid + liquorice powder	Orange yellow colour
For Tulsi: Alkaline reagent test: 0.5ml of crude extract+2ml of 2% NaOH	Intense Yellow colour
For Honey: fehling's reagent: aqueous solution of Honey+fehling's solution	Brick red colour

1. RESULT

1. Physical Evaluation:

Evaluation Test for Energy Drink

Table 4: Evaluation Test for Energy Drink

Test	Observation	Interference
1. Test for Carbohydrates: -1-2 drops of dilute iodine+1-2ml of sample	Red or Brown colour	Carbohydrates are present
2. Test for alkaloids: Dragendorff's test: 2-3ml of sample + few drops of Dragendorff's reagent solution	Orange brown ppt	Alkaloids are present
3. Test for Flavonoids: small amount of sample +lead acetate	Yellow colour ppt	Flavonoids are present
4. Test for Tannins and phenolic compounds: small amount of sample +acetic acid	Red colour	Tannins and phenolic compounds are present
5. Test for proteins: Small amount of sample +2ml of biuret reagent	Purple colour	Proteins are absent

6. Test for fats: small amount of sample on the filter paper dried in sunlight	Oily patch	Fats are absent
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CONCLUSION

The prepared formulation is beneficial for all the persons. The formulation is prepared from natural herbs so the chances of side effects are lower than soft drinks. This herbal energy drink is a natural option to synthetic drinks along with several health benefits. This is a good supplement for fresh recovery from illness and gives freshness to the person. All herbs used in this preparation are easily available during any season and are not costly; thus, the product is economically feasible.

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